

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONTENT AND STRUCTURE OF SCHOOL GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION IN POLAND AND UKRAINE

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Abstract

In the article, the authors performed a comparative analysis of the geography school curriculum in Poland and Ukraine. The authors found that in many parts these programs are similar. However, when studying the geography of Poland, greater emphasis is placed on the country's ties with EU countries, while when studying the nature and economy of Ukraine, greater emphasis is placed on Ukraine's place in the global space.

Keywords: geography, school, student, school education

According to Article 53 of the Constitution of Ukraine, every person has the right to receive an education. General secondary education is mandatory. The state guarantees the availability and free of charge of preschool and full general secondary education, as well as provides state scholarships and benefits for pupils and students. According to this provision, Ukrainian school education is compulsory and free. Complete secondary education in Ukraine lasts 12 years and consists of the following stages:

- Primary education (grades 1-4)
- Basic general secondary education (grades 5-9)
- Complete general secondary education (grades 10-12)

The first stage of education is primary education, which children can receive from the age of six or seven. In comprehensive schools, students receive primary and basic secondary education. After the 9th grade, students can choose to complete secondary education at school (grades 10-12) or to study at vocational colleges or schools for 4 years, which allows them to obtain a certificate of complete secondary education and certain professional qualifications. Young people finish the third (last) stage of general secondary education at the age of 18, when they become adults. After completing secondary school studies, students take the external examination, which allows them to enter higher educational institutions of Ukraine.

Compulsory education in Poland lasts 12 years. It can be divided into the following stages:

- Primary education (grades 1-8) - szkoła podstawowa
 - elementary school (grades 1-3)
 - 1st grade secondary school (grades 4-8)
- Second level secondary education - szkoła ponadpodstawowa - at the student's choice:

➤ General Lyceum (LO): an educational institution where each class is distinguished by its specialization, and studies last four years.

➤ Plastic Lyceum (art school): intended for children who are interested in general education and at the same time seek to acquire professional artistic skills. Education lasts five years.

➤ Technical College (T): an educational institution that provides a five-year secondary education along with professional skills.

➤ Branch school I level (SB I): the institution provides an opportunity to obtain qualifications in the chosen profession and studies here last for three years. After it, you can go to a branch school of level II (SB II), where you can supplement your professional education for two years.

During the primary school education period, there are two stages: primary school and upper secondary school, which last a total of 8 years.

In primary school (grades 1-3), teaching is conducted by the class teacher, except for certain subjects, such as music, physical education, foreign language and others. From the 4th to the 8th grade, children are taught by individual teachers in different directions.

Only in grades 6-8, children study individual subjects. During this period, there is a separate teacher for each subject. Children study Polish and foreign languages, mathematics, natural science, chemistry, physics, biology, history, music, art, physical education, informatics, work training, religion or ethics, and education for family life (consent for the child's participation in these subjects is accepted parents).

There is no such subject as "Geography" in elementary school in Ukraine, but students gain knowledge in this direction during the integrated course

"I explore the world" (grades 1-4). This subject is allocated in grades 1-4 for 3 hours per week in each class, where only 1 hour is allocated for the science component. In accordance with the Model Program, approved by the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated 12.08.2022 No. 743-22, in the course "I explore the world" the content lines "Man and nature" (knowledge of nature; the relationship of objects and natural phenomena; man-made world; responsible human activity in nature; the role of natural knowledge and technologies in human life; dependence between human activity and the state of the environment, human-nature relationships; human use of natural knowledge, materials, products and technologies; responsible activity of man in nature; rules of behavior in nature; children's participation in nature conservation activities), "Nature" (diversity of nature; methods of studying nature; inanimate and living nature; connections in nature; nature of the Earth; nature of Ukraine). These and other content lines of this integrated course are defined by the State Standard of Primary Education [5].

According to the Program, in the 1st grade, students study what belongs to nature, objects of living and non-living nature, learn to understand the need to preserve nature and its components. In the 2nd grade, students form an idea about the shape of the Earth; study the influence of the Sun on seasonal phenomena in nature; causes of changes in the seasons, observe daily and seasonal changes in nature; study the types of reservoirs, reservoirs of the native region; the main forms of the earth's surface; rocks; soil, its properties and significance, etc.

In the 3rd grade, students study the place of Ukraine on the world map; the country's place among European states; get acquainted with the diversity of peoples of the world; study the features, methods and tools of nature research; relationships between man and nature, the impact of human activity on nature, professions related to the study of nature.

In the 4th grade, students study the nearest neighboring countries of Ukraine, make virtual trips to other countries, study the cooperation of people in matters of preserving nature and life, the contribution of each person to the preservation of different cultures and natural resources. Deepen knowledge about the universe, the solar system, celestial bodies; consequences of rotation and movement of the Earth; learn about the natural zones of the Earth. In the 4th grade, students first get acquainted with the ways of depicting the Earth on geographic maps, globes, and terrain plans. They also study the peculiarities of the placement and formation of the nature of the Earth's continents and oceans. It is important in the 4th grade to turn the educational program to the study of the peculiarities of the geography of Ukraine, in particular when considering the questions: Nature of Ukraine. Ukraine on the world map. The most important natural objects of Ukraine and their area. Natural resources of Ukraine, their diversity and importance. Natural zones of Ukraine. Characteristics of the natural zone: natural conditions, flora and fauna, peculiarities of people's work and life. The impact of

human activity on nature. Seasonal changes in the nature of Ukraine. Natural groups. Folk traditions that reflect the attitude of Ukrainians to nature. Nature protection in Ukraine.

The purpose of science education for the primary grades of general high school is to promote the development of scientific thinking and the culture of research, the formation of systemic ideas about the integrity and diversity of nature, the establishment of principles of sustainable development, and the teaching of effective, safe and ecologically oriented behavior in the environment.

According to the above-mentioned goal, the key tasks of science education for primary school are:

- Cultivating a sense of respect and love for the nature of the native region, Ukraine and the Earth.

- Formation of ecological and ethical behavior in nature, stimulation of participation in nature conservation measures.

- Development of interest in the study of nature, mastering the methods of educational and cognitive activity and basic skills of scientific research through experiments and observations.

- Gradual formation of ideas about the natural and scientific picture of the world through the deepening of knowledge about natural objects and phenomena, their interrelationships in the system "inanimate nature - living nature", as well as awareness of human influence on the environment and its dependence on it.

In accordance with the goals and objectives of science education in elementary school, the following main directions are distinguished:

- "Nature" - aimed at developing students' research skills by supporting their curiosity and inquisitiveness towards observations, experiments and modeling to find answers to questions about the world around them.

- "Man and nature" - involves the development of younger schoolchildren's ideas about the objects and phenomena of nature, the establishment of connections between inanimate and living nature, the formation of a careful attitude towards nature and the skills of ecological behavior.

- "Man and the world" - aimed at forming general ideas about the world created by man, understanding the relationship between man and nature, which serves as a source for improving children's ideas and projects.

Research (observations, experiments), excursions, as well as students' activities in the field of nature protection and project work play a key role in natural science education.

In Poland, as well as in Ukraine, there is no separate subject "Geography" in primary grades; instead, students study the subject "Nature". The content of the training programs at this stage is similar, although the Ukrainian program is described in more detail than the Polish one. The difference is the absence in the Polish program of a specific list of topics and the number of hours allocated to them, as is done in the Ukrainian program.

According to the Concept of the "New Ukrainian School" and the State Standard of Basic Secondary Education, science education in Ukraine aims to develop students' natural and scientific competence, which is

the basis of the general culture of the individual and contributes to the development of their creative potential. This competence is based on a complex of approaches to the educational process, including competence, activity, integrative, person-oriented, research, problem-situational, differentiated and reflective approaches.

According to the State Standard of Basic Secondary Education, which will be implemented gradually from September 1, 2022, in the 2023/2024 academic year this standard will be applied to students of the 5th and 6th grades. Students of grades 7-11 will continue their studies according to the standard of basic and comprehensive general education of 2011.

According to these documents, as well as the Model Educational Program for grades 5-9, the educational process in the 5th-6th grades in the field of science education can be organized in the following ways:

1) according to model educational programs "Getting to know nature" for grades 5-6 with mandatory study of "Geography";

2) according to the model curriculum "Environment" for grades 5-6 with compulsory study of "Geography";

3) according to the model curriculum "Natural Sciences" for grades 5-6; the separate subject "Geography" is not studied, since the content of the geographical component is included in the "Natural Sciences" program.

In the 7th grade, during the "Continents and Oceans" course, students get acquainted with the nature of the continents, their physical and geographical features.

The study of geography in the 8th grade ("Ukraine in the world: nature, population") is aimed at creating a deep understanding of Ukraine as a component of the world community of states through comprehensive study. This course contributes to the formation of the student's sense of self-esteem as a citizen of Ukraine, fosters respect for the Ukrainian people, their culture, and stimulates a sense of patriotism. The course program provides 70 hours (2 hours per week), of which 3 hours are allocated for additional tasks.

The main principle of this course is integration, which combines physical and socio-geographic components in the study of natural complexes and the population of Ukraine and its regions, taking into account the knowledge gained during the study of world geography in the 6th and 7th grades. Special attention is paid to the study of the population of Ukraine on the basis of topics that have already been studied about the population of the world in previous courses, as well as at the expense of deepening this knowledge.

Geography in the 9th grade ("Ukraine and the world economy") completes basic geographic education at the basic level. This course is allocated 52 hours (1.5 hours per week), of which 3 hours are reserve time. The main goal of the course is to understand the trends in the development of the national and world economy, to determine the place of Ukraine in the modern world. Its content is built on the principle of integration, combining socio-geographic components while studying

the peculiarities of the development and structure of the economy in the world, Ukraine and its regions.

The program includes seven practical assignments, four of which are mandatory for assessment. They are aimed at developing skills for working with geographical maps and other sources of information, which helps in the further development of cognitive and professional skills. Also, students have to carry out research of their own choice, the results of which will be presented and evaluated by the teacher.

In the 10th grade, students get acquainted with the countries and regions of the modern world, the modern political map of the world, classifications of countries according to various characteristics, the structure and placement of branches of the world economy [6].

In the 11th grade, during the study of the course "Geographical space of the Earth", in essence, there is a repetition of the geographical knowledge of schoolchildren, which they acquired during the study of geography in grades 6-10 [6].

If we compare the contents of the geography program in the middle classes of Ukraine and Poland, it is worth saying that significant similarities can be traced in the 7th grade in Ukraine and in the 8th grade in Poland, when the entire academic year is devoted to the study of the continents and oceans of the world. Certain similarities can be traced in terms of the content of studying the geography of one's country. Both in the Polish and in the Ukrainian school curriculum, the study of the geography of one's country is integrated into the study of the geography of the world. However, in the Polish program, more emphasis is placed on placing Poland in the space of the EU countries and relations with them.

Then, as the study of Ukraine takes place in the global context. The geography of Poland is studied in the 7th grade, and in Ukraine, the geography of one's country is studied in the 8th and 9th grades. However, it is worth noting that in the 10th grade, during the study of individual countries of the European space (for example, Great Britain, Poland, etc.), a special emphasis is placed on the relations of these countries with Ukraine.

A similar feature of the geography programs of both countries is the study of their "Little Motherland". In the Polish program - in the 7th grade, and in the Ukrainian - in the 8th grade (Chapter V. Nature and population of its administrative region).

A comparison of the total number of hours allocated to the study of geography at school gives us the opportunity to state that, in general, this subject is taught in Ukraine by 170 hours more than in Poland. At the elementary school level, both countries have implemented an integrated course that combines knowledge from several disciplines, including and geography. However, the number of hours per year in Ukraine is 11 hours more in grades 1-4 than in Poland. In secondary classes, we see that the number of hours allocated to the study of geography in Ukraine is 2-2.5 times greater in individual classes than in Poland.

In senior classes in Ukraine (grades 10-11), 87 hours are allocated to geography, while in lyceums in Poland - 104 hours. What is similar is that high school

in both countries places a significant emphasis on studying global human problems and deepening knowledge of the geography sections that students studied in high school. However, in Poland, a whole year is devoted to a detailed study of the geography of their country - from the diversity of natural landscapes to the economy, cultural features, ethnography and environmental problems.

Conclusions. A comparison of the school geography curriculum in Poland and Ukraine shows significant similarities in the content and structure of both programs. A comparison of the total number of hours allocated to the study of geography at school gives us the opportunity to state that, in general, 162 more hours are taught in Ukraine than in Poland. At the primary school level, both countries have implemented an integrated course that combines knowledge from several disciplines, including geography. An important advantage of the Polish school curriculum in geography is its saturation with practical tasks and the inclusion of the geography of one's Little Motherland in the subject of study. The study of the geography of Poland takes place in conjunction with the study of the geography of the European region.

References:

1. Браславська О. Європейський досвід реформування географічної освіти. Проблеми підготовки сучасного вчителя. 2019. (17), 296–303.
2. Бойко В. М. Закордонний досвід розвитку географії рідного краю. Географія та основи економіки в школі. 2004. № 5. С. 28-29.
3. Василюк А. В. Реформи шкільної освіти в Польщі: історія й сучасність : [монографія]. Ніжин : Вид-во НДУ ім. М. Гоголя, 2007. 340 с.
4. Глушко О. Модернізаційний вимір шкільної освіти у Польщі: ключові тенденції розвитку. Український Педагогічний журнал. 2019 (4). 32–41.
5. Навчальна програма для закладів загальної середньої освіти. Географія (6-9 класи). Затверджена наказом Міністерства освіти і науки України від 03 серпня 2022 року № 698. URL: <https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/zagalna%20serednya/programy-5-9-klas/2022/08/15/navchalna.programa-2022.geography-6-9.pdf>
6. Навчальна програма для закладів загальної середньої освіти. Географія (10-11 класи). Рівень стандарту. Затверджена наказом Міністерства освіти і науки України від 03 серпня 2022 року № 698. URL: <https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/zagalna%20serednya/programy-10-11-klas/2022/08/15/navchalna.programa-2022.geography-10-11-standart.pdf>
7. Модельні навчальні програми для 5-9 класів Нової Української Школи. Природничі освітні галузь (5-6 класи). URL: <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/osvita/zagalna-serednya-osvita/navchalni-programi/modelni-navchalni-programi-dlya-5-9-klasiv-novoyi-ukrayinskoyi-shkoli-zaprovadzhuyutsya-poetapno-z-2022-roku>